

FORMATION OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Speech competence, in the form of a monologue, the ability to conduct a discussion, communicative competence, the act of communication, communication of information, the formation of language and speech competencies, the norms of the Russian literary language and the rules of speech culture, ways of interacting with surrounding people and events, possession of the richness of language as a condition for successful speech activity, communicative competence means willingness to put and achieve the goal of oral and written communication.

ABSTRACT

In modern society, the formation of speech competence is of great interest, since there is a big problem associated with a clear lack of language education, low language competence of the majority of the population. Therefore, a person should learn to master the basic skills: to think independently, to look for the most correct ways to overcome difficulties; to possess a rich vocabulary, to be sociable, to work independently on their own development. In this regard, the requirements for teaching Russian language and literature include the formation of not only linguistic, but also speech competence of students related to the culture of oral and written speech, rules and methods of using language in different speech situations.

Let's try to identify the main reasons why there are problems with mastering communicative skills - The communicative aspect of speech culture remains not fully developed. Modern textbooks still cannot sufficiently ensure the formation of speech communication skills in various life situations.

What is speech competence?

All knowledge about the world is comprehended through language, through language. Language is not only a mental gymnastics and the main means of communication, but also the main tool for the formation of national identity. Speech competence is part of the communicative competence.

Speech competence – fluent practical command of speech, the ability to speak correctly, fluently and dynamically both in dialogue and in the form of a monologue, to understand audible and readable speech well, including the ability to produce and understand speech in any style, i.e. the ability to use the accumulated language material in speech for the purpose of communication.

The following tasks of a teacher can be distinguished.

1. Teach how to work with text (highlight the main idea, search for the necessary information, analyze it, make generalizations and conclusions);
2. To form the ability to conduct a discussion, listen and hear the interlocutor, defend your point of view, supported by arguments;
3. Develop the skills of creating new texts, increase the creative potential of students, verbal and logical thinking.

What is communicative competence, competence approach?

Competence includes a set of interrelated personality qualities (knowledge, skills, skills, methods of activity), set in relation to a certain range of subjects and processes and necessary for high-quality productive activity in relation to them. It turns out that competence for a student is an image of his future, a reference point for mastering.

Communication– an act of communication, a connection between two or more individuals based on mutual understanding, the communication of information by one person to another or a number of persons.

Communicative competence includes knowledge of the necessary languages, ways of interacting with other people and events, group work skills, knowledge of various social roles in the team. The student should be able to introduce himself, write a letter, a questionnaire, an application, ask a question, conduct a discussion. Language competence presupposes knowledge of the language itself, its structure and functioning, language norms, including spelling and punctuation.

Communicative competence is not only the ability to understand others and generate one's own statements, speech behavior adequate to the goals, spheres, situations of communication, it includes knowledge of basic speech concepts: styles, types of speech, structure of description, narration, reasoning, ways of linking sentences in the text, the ability to analyze the text. In this regard, the communicative approach requires new methods, forms and means of teaching, special organization of educational material. In addition, the communicative approach involves the study of linguistic units, taking into account their functions and interaction in speech, the assimilation of the features of the functioning of grammatical forms and structures in various types and styles of speech, i.e. the study of the facts of language in the unity of their form, meaning and function.

Language proficiency means the ability to act in compliance with the norms of the Russian literary language and the rules of speech culture. Every cultured person should be familiar with the diverse dictionaries and reference books on the Russian language and be able to use them in all doubtful cases.

Unfortunately, students have serious shortcomings in the development of communicative competence. What are the reasons?

- decrease in the level of reader culture;
- reduction of the level of individual vocabulary;
- low level of formation of individual and personal grounds for communicative competence.

Language competence

Language competence is the ability of students to use words, their forms, syntactic structures in accordance with the norms of the literary language, to use its synonymic

structures in accordance with the norms of the literary language, to use its synonymic means, ultimately – possession of the richness of the language as a condition for successful speech activity. These tasks are traditionally solved by introducing new layers of vocabulary, replenishing the phraseological stock, enriching the grammatical structure of students' speech: morphological norms of coordination, management, construction of sentences of different types are assimilated, students' speech is enriched with synonymous constructions.

It is language and communicative competencies that contribute to the formation of speech communication skills. And for this, it is necessary to create conditions for speech communication at each lesson. Speech activity is formed in all its forms – reading, speaking, writing, listening. "To teach communication by communicating" – there is no lesson without these conditions.

Communicative competence means the willingness to set and achieve the goals of oral and written communication: to receive the necessary information, to represent and defend one's point of view in a civilized manner in dialogue and in public speaking based on recognition of the diversity of positions and respect for the values (religious, ethnic, professional, personal, etc.) of other people.

Communication potential.

This is a characteristic of a person's capabilities, which determine the quality of his communication. It includes, along with competence in communication, two more components: communicative personality traits that characterize the development of the need for communication, attitude to the method of communication and communicative abilities – the ability to own initiative in communication, the ability to be active, emotionally respond to the state of communication partners, formulate and implement their own individual communication program, the ability to self-stimulation and to mutual stimulation in communication.

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